

FORMING STUDENTS' CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of wide use of activities that develop critical thinking in English language classes. As a result of the use of modern approaches and innovative methods, such as the development of critical thinking in English language teaching, the development of students' logical thinking skills, fluency in speech, the formation of quick and correct response skills, instilling enthusiasm for knowledge and the English language lessons about the importance of a creative approach.

Key words: teaching English, critical thinking, creative approach, speaking skills. One of the most fundamental and positive changes in modern primary education is the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" is Resolution No. PQ-1875. On the basis of this decision, learning foreign languages, mainly English, from the 1st grade of general secondary schools in the form of game-style lessons and oral speech lessons, and from the 2nd grade, the alphabet, reading and grammar teaching begins step by step. Incomparable large-scale work has been started in all directions of the education field to further develop the study of foreign languages. For example, from the 2013-2014 academic year, continuous teaching of foreign languages in the form of game-style exercises and oral speech lessons was launched in the first grades of general education schools. The intended textbook and educational-methodical sets were created. It is worth noting that the games in the complexes created for the first grades are proportional to the age of the children.

Today's demand is to educate mature and independent thinkers, which requires to improve the process of education, development of new directions of work with students and striving for unconventionality. Accordingly, in order to educate young students to think, search and consciously acquire knowledge and expand their worldview, it requires a variety of methods. One of such new technologies is the formation of critical thinking skills in students. In elementary school students, through critical thinking, the ability to think logically, worldview, along with skills such as independent and free thinking, analysis, comparison, interpretation of thoughts, discussion, protection of one's ideas and pursuit of news. important features such as self-awareness, communicative

literacy, being able to feel and enjoy beauty and sophistication, being mentally and physically healthy, absorbing and appreciating national traditions are developed. This, in turn, ensures that students of younger ages can deeply absorb knowledge and correctly apply it in practice. Accordingly, in order to develop the critical thinking of elementary school students, it is important to design the purpose of the lesson on the basis of a clear pedagogical technology. There are many unexplored things in life. Curiosity develops the mind. Curiosity leads to discoveries and adventures. By developing the ability to be interested in what is happening, it not only develops critical thinking, but also makes life richer and more colorful.

The importance of critical thinking in teaching foreign languages is incomparable, and at present, increasing critical thinking in students is one of the tasks of foreign language teachers. Many different factors can affect students' critical thinking skills. M. Lipman, S. Norris, and R. Ennis, who conducted research in the field of education, presented their approaches to critical thinking. There are no big differences in the definitions given by them, according to L. Elder and R. Paul, critical thinking is the ability of individuals to manage their own thinking and develop appropriate criteria and standards for analyzing their own thoughts. In addition, as V. Maiorana noted, critical thinking is a process aimed at understanding and evaluating different points of view and solving problems. The skills required to be able to think critically are varied and include observation, analysis, interpretation, reflection, evaluation, inference, explanation, problem solving and decision making. Although the importance of applying critical thinking lessons to students of all ages is immeasurable, we must remember our role as teachers and what we need to do to achieve their goals, and we must always organize lessons with these aspects in mind. .

Certain aspects of the process of forming critical thinking in students are based on the following foundations:

- Coordination of the speed of the study process;
- Increasing the student's enthusiasm for studying;
- Taking previously acquired knowledge into account;
- Support the student's initiative and commitment;
- Learning by doing;
- Organization of bilateral exchange of opinions;
- Set up the study process correctly;
- Facilitating the learning process for teachers and students;
- Evaluation of the educational process

In the process of learning, students' critical thinking creates multifaceted activities, and in the process of transitioning from one type of activity to another, each student develops the ability to determine his personal, specific goal. This goal creates the ground for students to engage in independent, creative activities and is the basis for developing a strict program of action.

The technology of forming critical thinking in students is implemented by pedagogues by performing special types of assignments, independent activities, and their effectiveness is realized with the help of certain criteria. If the educational process is fully directed to the student, organized on the basis of certain principles, taking into account his needs and opportunities, interests, talent, then the results of such education, first of all, are the personality of the student, along with the state, society and the factor that develops science and production. It is recommended to start using critical thinking in the classroom from a young age, and it is important to adapt the lessons to the children's age, but it is important to focus on allowing them to use their intellectual abilities as much as possible. the basis for the formation of critical thinking is created in them.

Starting from the second grade, other educational games aimed at mastering grammar can be organized. For example, interesting games such as "Who is literate?", "Who is clever?", "Who am I?", "Chain", "Role-playing game", "Find the place of the word" are among them. "Who's smart?" game gives a good result in improving spelling literacy. In this case, 5-6 words are written on cardboard, and the words are written correctly and incorrectly. Students are required to find the misspelled word and write it correctly. The winner of the game is determined by which student is the first to correctly write the misspelled words. In the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach independent thinking. Research shows that critical thinking is not an innate or naturally formed ability, but it is no exaggeration to say that critical thinking is a taught and learned process. Extensive use of activities that develop critical thinking in the classroom - foreign language teachers require high skills from the teacher in order to provide a quality learning experience to their students.

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